

A WOMAN'S TRIUMPH IN A MALE- DOMINATED WORLD IN "THE QUEEN'S GAMBIT" BY WALTER TEVIS

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Abstract: *This article analyzes the importance of women in society, their comparison with men, and the presence of gender inequality in the "Queen's Gambit". The protagonist's great achievements are often ignored because of her gender. When a famous male chess master defeats a chess player, the press emphasizes that she is playing chess as a woman, not her chess strategy or moves. The article is not limited to one topic, but also includes other topics such as the social and psychological development of the protagonist, how she inspires readers. Through this article, we will be introduced with several examples of how gender inequality prevents women from fully demonstrating their talents, and we will see evidence that being capable is not a concept related to gender, but to interest, action, and other factors.*

Keywords: *psychological development, chess, gender inequality, demonstrating talents, orphanage girl.*

Introduction: In the late 20th century, gender equality was considered a major global social issue. Women faced low pay, limited job opportunities, and educational opportunities in many workplaces.

Table 1. Gender Inequality Index, 1990-2010

The chart above shows the Gender Inequality Index from 1990 to 2010. Sub-Saharan Africa is the most affected region by gender inequality. In East Asia and the Pacific, the index has gradually moved from average to low. In particular, Europe and Central Asia have lower gender inequality than other countries. From this chart, we can see that in many regions, gender inequality has decreased, but it is still a problem that has not been completely eliminated.

1.1. Gender Bias in Professional Spheres.

If we look back to a not so distant past, a century ago, we can witness gender inequality as a black spot in society. This issue has long been the reason why women have been portrayed as weak heroines in the process of development, women have faced many problems for their gender, for example, Emily Bronte presented her work to the public under the pseudonym of a man - Ellis Bell, and the main reason for this was the stereotypes formed in the minds of people in society about women as weak and less capable than men. Their achievements were even mentioned only by their full names. In particular, scientific fields were not seen as areas where women could demonstrate their skills and capabilities, and Rosalind Franklin, who contributed immensely to the development of the structure of DNA, who conducted equally important research along with other male scientists of the same sex, was mentioned much less in the publication sources where this discovery was mentioned compared to her other male colleagues. But if we look at the pages of history, women are no different from men according to their achievements and opportunities. They can be successful in any field. Marie Curie was awarded the Nobel Prize for her physics research and radioactive studies at a time when men were considered superior in science. Or the success of Ella Fitzgerald, who was able to fully express her voice and talent in the field of Jazz, which was considered not for women, deserves strong recognition with her high voice and art. According to the opinions and analyses in the article presented to the public by Racusin (2012), the view of men as stronger dominant figures than women in society is very strong. This research and analysis leads to the conclusion that professors, despite the fact that both sexes have the same qualifications, provided more opportunities for male students and supported them more. In this case, we can see the existence of a subtle gender bias. The most disturbing point is that changing the gender of the professors did not affect the

change in the resulting opinions. That is, female professors also considered their own gender, female students, to be inferior and less capable than men. From this we can see that gender inequality has been a problem of the times, and even until now this problem has not been completely solved.

1.2. The making of a world chess champion

As an influential author of the late twentieth century, Walter Tevis (1928-1984) played a key role in writing "Queen's Gambit", a masterpiece that explores a young girl's ability to overcome social barriers and achieve success in a male-dominated field. The events of "Queen's Gambit" begin in the 1980s. When the main character of the work, Elizabeth, is 9 years old, her mother dies and she ends up in the Methuen orphanage. She feels lonely in the orphanage, after seeing the janitor Shaibel playing chess in the basement she becomes very interested in chess. At first, the janitor tells her that girls don't play chess, but later Beth Harmon skillfully learns the rules of the game. Beth practiced playing chess with Mr. Shaibel every Sunday. Furthermore, The orphanage gives the girls green pills-tranquilizers, and Elizabeth becomes addicted to them. Taking the pills, she begins to play chess on the ceiling in a dream at night. After some years, she is adopted by the Wheatley family. Her mother, Alma Wheatley, helps Beth, and Elizabeth begins to win money by participating in various chess games and tournaments. She even wins state championships, impressing male chess players. But she loses to the world's best chess player, Vasily Borgov. The reason for her defeat is that after the death of her mother, she became addicted to alcohol and drugs. Then her friends - Harry Beltik, Benny Watts and her friend from the orphanage - Jolene call her and help her analyze her opponent's games. Finally, she defeated Borgov and became the world champion. This is not only her victory over chess, but also her own fears. She proved that women can also be the strongest chess players.

Literary review

"The Queen's Gambit" novel is not just a simple book for people to read, it has also been a real motivation that has been able to arouse interest and enthusiasm for this game among many people, especially young girls, in the real world. According to Keene (2020), this masterpiece has made a special contribution to the historical and cultural significance and popularity of chess, and the increased interest

in this game around the world has inspired many inspired players. This work has had such a strong impact on the popularization of chess that the author of the article even considers its impact to be second only to the world championship between Bobby Fischer and Boris Spassky.

In addition, Mangan (2020) has proven with her thoughts that it can also be a strong motivation for ordinary people to find their own way. According to him, the story of the main character Elizabeth Harmon, who rose from an ordinary girl in an orphanage to a great chess master, can be a real motivation for many, especially girls and women. You don't have to understand chess to be inspired by this work. Because it tells a story about a more interesting topic than chess for readers, namely, human growth, the struggle for success, the obstacles on this path and the achievement of victory.

Some believe that people's inner world and personal changes are more important. As an example of such views, we can cite the ideas analyzed in the article by Andrew(2021). What the author wants to show is that chess is not just a simple game for Elizabeth Harmon, but a means of managing her life and understanding herself. Internal problems are more complex concept than failures or successes in life, and the main character of the work cannot stop struggling with her internal problems even though she has many victories. At the beginning of the novel, she is somewhat dependent on things and people around her, but over time she becomes a strong independent girl who can make her own decisions and it made this novel a story of personal growth.

This unique work does not choose an age for reading, it is equally enjoyable for everyone. Its mass influence is so strong that it has even changed the personal interests of people. Kwasnick (2021) expressed her thoughts on the impressions this work has made on readers and how much it has influenced them.

Ultimately, this is not just a story about chess, but it is about personal growth . The story encourages everyone to work hard for their goals, never give up, and overcome their inner difficulties, showing Beth Harmon's journey from orphanage to world champion . Even if you don't understand chess, the story teaches you that true success comes from hard work, freedom, and working on mistakes.

Methodology

The article mainly uses literary analysis methods to analyze the given topic. The main guide is the author's work, "Queen's Gambit", and various articles and essays are used as additional sources. The textual analysis method is also important in explaining how Beth Harmon rose to leadership in a male-dominated environment.

Discussion

The Queen's Gambit of Walter Tevis contains gender inequality between the two sexes. Walter Tevis clearly showed this in his work. As an example, in the first chapter of the novel, Elizabeth sees the janitor playing chess and asks him to teach her. But Mr. Shaibel insists that he does not teach strangers, and Elizabeth tells him that she is not a stranger and has already learned some of the rules of chess by observing him.

"I'm not a stranger," she said to him two days later. "I live here." Behind her head a small moth circled the bare bulb, and its pale shadow crossed the board at regular intervals. "You can teach me. I already know some of it, from watching."

"Girls don't play chess." Mr. Shaibel's voice was flat. (Chapter 1, p.13)

As mentioned in this section, Mr. Shaibel is reluctant to teach her chess because she is a girl. In order to dispel the notion that chess is only for men, Beth has to ask again and again.

"We don't have a women's section," he said. She just stared at him. "I'll put you in Beginners," he said. "No," Beth said, "I'm not a beginner." The other young man had been watching them. "If you're an unrated player, you go in Beginners with the people under sixteen hundred," he said (Chapter 4, p.74)

In this episode, during registration for the Kentucky State Championships, Beth is treated with disdain by the organizers. The male registrant doubts her skills and tells her that because she is unrated and a girl, she will compete with the lowest-ranked players. We see Elizabeth Harmon being ignored by a male organizer because she is a girl when she registers. The male organizer treats her as a beginner and thinks she is inferior to other male chess players. If she doesn't have a rating, she is automatically told that she will have to play at a lower level. This shows that she will have to work harder than others to show her ability. By

winning all the games, the heroine of the story is able to destroy the stereotype that chess is a male game and that girls are inferior to it.

"Then she began asking questions. Her manner was pleasant and direct. "I've really been impressed," she said, "even I can not play chess myself." She smiled."They say you're the real thing."Beth was a little embarrassed."How does it feel?Being a girl among all those men?" "Is not it frightening ?" (Chapter 5, p.108)

During an interview for "Life " magazine, a journalist asks Elizabeth questions about the fact that she is a girl, not about the rules of chess. This topic shows that a woman's gender is considered more important than her success.

"When I was a girl," the reporter said, "I was never allowed to be competitive. I used to play with dolls."(Chapter 5, p.108)

With this question, the reporter is expressing his opinion against young girls participating in chess games. Elizabeth is trying to say that she is still a little girl, at the age of playing with dolls.

Furthermore, in the novel Beth and Beltik compete in the first state championship. Beltik does not see Elizabeth as a serious opponent, thinking that girls can never win. But Beth surprises him by checkmating him. Moreover, when analyzing her game with Ber Borgov, Russian chess players treat her with disdain. They think that she is a weak girl who grew up in an orphanage. There is a wrong concept that women are always weaker than men. In addition, Harmon's adoptive mother Alma Wheatley is also a victim of gender inequality. She was originally a brilliant pianist, but after marriage, her husband did not allow her to play the piano, so she became an alcoholic and addicted to drugs at home, becoming an "unhappy housewife".

Conclusion:

To summarize our thoughts, "Queen's Gambit" can help women gain self-confidence and show their abilities. No girl or woman is stronger than a man in any field, but no less. It is through "Queen's Gambit" that we can witness this. We can say that gender inequality can lead to many problems, discrimination and arrogance. Because women are no less than men in terms of strength, intelligence and ability. The examples we have seen above can be seen as clear proof of our words. It is a very wrong and stupid idea to single out women only because of their gender, to see them as weak and incapable people. The results of various studies and the achievements of women in many

fields prove that this deeply held stereotype among the public is actually wrong. "The Queen's Gambit" work shows the readers that gender does not limit any ability. In the world of chess, where men are more numerous and superior, the fact that women face trials and difficulties, limitations, and nevertheless overcome the wall of difficulties they face through their mental strength and skill is commendable. Through this work, we can conclude that women can overcome male opponents not only in chess but also in other fields through their experience, skills, and relentless effort. If we think deeper, gender is not a limiting factor and a means of separating the strong from the weak.

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